

Factors Influencing Implementation of Social Protection Projects In Kamukunji Sub County, Nairobi Kenya

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to establish factors influencing the implementation of social protection projects in Kamukunji Sub County. The study was informed by resource based theory which was linked to resources availability. The research used descriptive research design. The population sample size was 198 respondents drawn from Kamukunji Sub County. The study findings indicated that the four variables that are managerial skills, Resource mobilization positively and significantly affect the implementation of social protection projects in Kamukunji Sub County. The study recommends that future studies should focus on other sectors. The study sought to find out the relationship between managerial skills and implementation of projects, from the findings the respondents agreed that managerial skills influence implementation of social protection projects, with specific emphasis on technical ability and interpersonal proficiency and conceptual expertise. From the findings, the respondents agreed that resource mobilization affects the implementation of social protection projects.

Keywords; *Managerial Skills, Resource Mobilization, Factors, Implementation, Social, Projects*

Introduction

Social protection is regular and predictable transfers, often in the form of cash, provided by the state as part of a social contract with its citizens (DFID, 2006). They include child support grants, orphan care grants, disability grants, social pensions, and transfers to poor households, among others. Their objective is to alleviate poverty, provide social protection, or reduce economic vulnerability. Some cash transfers may be unconditional; others are conditional, aimed to promote particular behaviors, such as school attendance or regular health checkups (Development Policy Review, 2006). Social protection projects are concerned with preventing, managing, and overcoming situations that adversely affect people's Dignity, well-being and cushion them against vulnerabilities (United Nations Research Institute, 2010). Social protection consists of policies and programs designed to reduce poverty and vulnerability by promoting efficient labor markets and diminishing people's exposure to risks. It enhances the capacity to manage economic and social risks, such as unemployment, exclusion, ill health, disability and old age.

Traditionally, social protection has been used in the European welfare state and other parts of the developed world to maintain a certain living standard, and address transient poverty. In the research which examines the significance of social protection programs on the livelihoods of small farming households in the Brazilian Amazon estuary region. Several social programs have been conducted in this region, including Bolsa Familia that aims to increase children's education, an old age pension, and a closing fishing compensation. Together, they constitute a major income source for impoverished farming households facing increasing stress from both nature and society (e.g., more frequent and more severe tidal floods, crop price oscillation). Overall, social programs constitute half of the households' annual income, and almost ten percent of all households rely solely on social protection projects. Although most programs are designed for children and seniors, this cash income may play an important role in the household's decision making, e.g., investing in a bigger boat for fishing. It is also possible that this may create a dependence on cash transfers as shown by other studies (Bertrand, 2003; Kassouf and de Oliveira, 2012).

The proportion of a household's total income represented by cash transfers (1) provides an indicator of the level of dependence of the household on the cash transfers and (2) represents how households assemble different livelihood activities (e.g., highly-dependent on forest resources to generate income) to fulfill their subsistence and investment requirements (Babulo et al., 2008; Mamo et al., 2007; Mohammad Abdullah et al., 2016). The choice of "dependence" here does not have a negative indication; it is rather a neutral representation of the percentage. The combination of livelihood activities and the size of cash transfers received by households form a livelihood strategy that is used to maintain the livelihood and well-being of the household. The factors affecting the strategies that can be formed and their application are constrained by livelihood assets (e.g., goods, food, services, money) and capacity constraints of the household. Due to the heterogeneous distribution of livelihood assets among households, two households receiving the same social protection programs may adopt different livelihood strategies, resulting in different levels of dependence on cash transfers.

In addition to cash transfer programs, an important livelihood option for low-income rural farming communities is the participation in off-farm activities. A majority of the rural poor have actively pursued off-farm activities, and income from these activities plays an important role in rural livelihoods. For example, more than half of farm households' income in the Mexican ejido sector is from off-farm activities (De Janvry and Sadoulet, 2001). In the Brazilian Amazon estuary region, households establish residences in both rural and urban areas to facilitate income generation from off-farm activities (Padoch et al., 2008). Off-farm activities contribute to rural poverty reduction, increased income, and have positive spillover effects on agricultural activities (e.g., allow farmers to invest in productivity-enhancing inputs with cash from non-farm activities when credit is unavailable), which constitute a new approach in rural development and may also affect the efficacy of cash transfer programs. However, the pursuit of off-farm activities may move rural households away from agricultural and agro-forestry activities. This can increase the wealth of these former agricultural households by having a stable wage every month. However, it may also result in a loss of traditional knowledge, or a higher risk of exposure to job market failure, especially when it is only labor-intensive work.

Over 53% of Kenya's population lives under the poverty line, which means that 8.6 million children are in urgent need of support. An estimated 12 % of all Kenyan are children less than 18 years of age, and 1 million are persons with Disabilities and Vulnerable (National Survey for persons with Disabilities 2007/2008). Due to the ongoing upward trending poverty, fragmented development, and Disability prevalence nationally, increasing numbers of persons with disabilities are growing up without adequate support, care, and protection. Children and women suffer double vulnerability compared with other children and women, for example in nutrition and access to education (De-Neubourg, 2009).

As entrenched in the social pillar of the Kenya vision 2030 blueprint and the constitution of Kenya, resources distribution and improved livelihoods for all vulnerable groups and people with disabilities is a flagship project. The ministry of labor and Social Protection has managed the cash transfers program for PWSD since 2010 and currently at a total of 47,200 beneficiaries (Source Data NCPWDs March 2018). The planning and implementation of this program have seen several changes and improvements. At least 80% of initial beneficiaries have consistently been receiving cash benefits. These beneficiaries are expected to have been brought out of stigmatization and discrimination.

Kenya's main social protection projects reach, directly or indirectly, an estimated 7.5% of the total child Population. Despite progress in expanding the number of beneficiaries, Kenya's cash transfer does not yet reach the vast majority of persons with severe disabilities in the poorest wealth Quintiles, even though coverage is pro-poor. Another major gap in the system is the very low coverage of children with severe disabilities and are underrepresented in the PWSD-CT and to the lesser extent in the other programs too. This goes against one of the key principles of disability sensitive social protection projects to intervene as early as possible where persons with disabilities are at risk to prevent irreversible impairment or harm.

The Kenya main social protection projects offer similar transfer value of Kshs. 2,000 per month per beneficiary household, while the HSNP has a higher value of Kshs. 2,700. Currently, all schemes operate as household benefits rather than individual entitlements offering a fixed amount regardless of the household size or composition. The result is that the system as a whole does not respond to differences in vulnerability between households. So, a household with more than one person with a severe disability will only receive a single PWSD-CT. This means there is an insufficient support to address the additional needs of the household effects. Therefore, the effectiveness of the system as a whole is reduced as a result of the household transfers.

As part of the implementation of the Convention on Rights of Persons with Disabilities, (CRPD) which Kenya ratified and signed in 2007 and 2008 respectively the government also enacted the Social Assistance Act No, 24 of 2013/29 which provides that a person with a disability is entitled to social assistance. The beneficiaries of the scheme have gradually increased in the past financial years to the current number being 94 persons with severe disabilities per Sub County/ constituency. PWSDs are persons whose needs were not being addressed in any other way. The perceived needs include poverty, poor health, Stigma and exclusion from mainstream society. The cash benefits are expected to cushion them against suffering from hunger, illiteracy, and disease. Other forms of abuse for PWSDs are neglect and discrimination from sharing equal rights like other members of the household and society at large.

The cash transfer program for PWSDs was specifically designed to meet the needs of these specific categories of persons. However, like constraints in a project, the program has also faced various challenges. According to Csete (2001), a great number of persons with severe disabilities have not benefited effectively from the projects. This greatly risks the future of the projects as it may continue to produce undesired effects. Although the efforts are impressive, it requires developing programmatic structures and processes necessary to deliver the benefits and to monitor the processes and outcomes. Therefore, the thrust of this research was to find out the factors influencing the effective implementation of social protection programs in Kamukunji sub-county Nairobi County.

Theoretical Review

Resource Based View Theory was linked to resource mobilization variable. Resource mobilization is the maximizing on the use of the existing funds. Werner and Rumelt established Resource based view theory in 1984. The resource based view of the firm (RBV) explains that each institution or organization has unique resources and capabilities that make them different hence becomes a competitive advantage (Muthuuri, 2014). Initiated in the mid-1980s, the resource-based view (RBV) has since become one of the leading modern methods to the analysis of sustained competitive advantage (Tan & Meyer, 2010). The theory on RBV offers a good explanation of how the sub counties and counties can make good use of their financial resources provided by the government in implementing the various projects in the areas. Resource based view theory is of importance in ensuring projects and programs is maximizing on use of existing funds. Resource based view theory is of importance in ensuring that other sources of funds are available and accounted for. Sustainability of projects is also very important in order to avoid stalling projects.

Empirical Framework

This section will present and expound on the empirical review which discusses the past studies by other authors and scholars. The empirical literature is discussed as per the study variable which is the managerial skills, resource mobilization on the social protection projects.

Managerial skills

Karimi (2014) study on the role of projects in improving households welfare in Nkaimurunya division Ngong district of Kajiado county discovered to be doing poorly, lack of training. She believes that a trained business person will be able to evaluate the course of a venture in view of both internal and external forces and fix any deviation if identified. One who lacks skills may undergo training since the projects they're implementing may not accomplish the intended objectives

According to Czerniawska and Toppin (2010) manual operations which depend on bare strength are steadily being phased out in projects execution, and instead, technology is replacing human labor geared towards obtaining maximum gains, while reducing the cost of projects. This is an indication that soon, only skilled personnel will be required rendering large population of untrained workers jobless. Strategies that are superior in nature are developed for use in organizations through manipulation of internalized skills and knowledge learned through training and refined by experience.

According to Mason (2013), training and education offer the greatest asset to an organization. Investing in human capital with the request skills and knowledge prove a worthy undertaking because workers with a wealth of knowledge make resources more productive. Whereas some organizations may choose to invest heavily in non-human resources, in business, one must realize that success begins with resource deployment, and therefore resources must be allocated based on thoroughly throughout plans, which can effectively be done by trained personnel.

In India where bricks are being made and this industry provides employment to several rural folks is being regarded as a great pollutant of the environment when undertaken in its traditional form. With the introduction of brick-making machines, this sector has been improved. Several brick making persons have been trained in using the technology making these projects productive. These studies revealed above indicate that technical capacity is vital for the implementation of projects (Mason, 2013). Of specific relevance in this study is its relevance to project managers who need to have the necessary management skills in the implementation and performance of projects sponsored by the government.

Resources mobilization

Obiero (2013) argued that social, economic factors affecting farm yield in siaya county established that due to lack of resources to put up green shades for selling agricultural products such maize, fruits, vegetables, and Irish potatoes, sellers resorted to lining directly along the road with their products targeting potential customers on transit and exposing them to diverse weather conditions.

Investigating the influence of financial resources on the implementation of small projects ventures in the cottage industry in India, Rondinelli (2013) indicated that cottage projects started with the production of simple households, but have improved over time. surprisingly the traditional industrial nations of the world with popular industrial products. He observed that this great milestone achieved in the growth of cottage industry in India was facilitated by the government's interest in allocating funds to the industry as it was creating job opportunities for the citizen. He further noted that it was because of the growth of the cottage industry in India that saw the growth of the economy and the expansion of projects that helps the community at large.

Research gaps

Different studies have been done in different industries on the effectiveness of cash based programs intervention Kamau, L.W and Kagiri, A.W (2015) studied the influence of cash transfer program on organizational competitiveness. They looked at how cash impact, availability and the source of the firm cash. Mogere, Oloko and Okibo, (2013) investigated the impact of cash transfers on orphans and single mothers in sub Saharan

Africa. This study carried out the factors influencing the effective implementation of social protection projects in Kamukunji Sub County. The study outlined the following variables, managerial skills, resource mobilization, monitoring and evaluation, and the stakeholder's involvement. Studies have been done on other areas but not in the selected constituency, a gap this study sought to fill.

Methods

This study used descriptive research design which involved the gathering of data that describes events then organizing, tabulating depicting and describing the data. A total sample size of 198 respondents was taken with the aid of Yamane (1967) formula: $n=N/(1+e^2)$. stratified random sampling was the most suitable method to be used in the selection of the respondents in each subgroup while simple random sampling used to select respondents in the strata. This research used a questionnaire to collect primary data. The pilot study was carried out on 10 respondents who are sufficient based on Glesne (2015) who stated that 10% of the population is adequate to constitute the pilot test size. Content validity formula by Amin (2005) used in this study. The researcher conducted a preliminary analysis to test for reliability using Cronbach's alpha.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data in frequency distributions and percentages which was presented in tables and figures. Discussions and presentations of the analyzed data were done in tables of frequency distribution, percentages, bar graphs, and pie charts. Measures of dispersion were used to provide information about the spread of the scores in the distribution. The study was also adopted multiple regression analysis to test the relationships between the variables. In the study, a statistical model was developed from the conceptual framework that was as follows: the dependent variable (DV) which in this study was implementation of social protection projects take the variable [Y], and the coefficients of the independent variables (IV) denoted by X_1, X_2, \dots, X_4 was used to show the relationship of the independent variables. Statistically, the analysis was carried out using the models.

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

Y_i Implementation of effective social protection projects, X_1 - managerial skills, X_2 - Resources Mobilization β_i ($i=1, 2, 3, 4$) are the parameters associated with the corresponding independent variable that are to be estimated (partial regression coefficients)

β_0 is the intercept; ε is the error variability (error term).

Findings And Discussion

The study sampled 198 respondents from which 112 filled in and returned the questionnaires making a response rate of 56.6 %. This response rate was adequate to make conclusions on the factors influencing the implementation of social protection projects in Kamukunji Sub County. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2008), a response rate of 50% is adequate for analysis and reporting; a rate of 60% is good, and a response of 70% and above is excellent.

Descriptive and Correlation Analysis

From the findings, it's clear that managerial skills are important in implementing social protection projects. As such, implementation of projects is strongly affected by managerial skills. The findings are in tandem with Rambo *et al.* (2015) who concluded that successful projects in any community or organization require good managerial skills, guiding principles, strategies of empowerment, participation, multidisciplinary, collaboration, and equity.

From the findings, it was clear that resource mobilization influence implementation of social protection projects with more emphasis on resources availability, financial adequacy, and human capital. It's clear from the findings that proper resource mobilization influences the time, scope and cost of implementing social protection projects. The findings concur with Nysten *et al.*, (2010) who concluded lack of resources to put up green shades in Siaya County for selling agricultural products had made sellers resort to lining directly along the road with their products exposing them to adverse weather conditions. In addition, the findings agree with Kabega (2016) who concluded that the great milestone achieved by the cottage industries in India was facilitated by the government interest in allocating funds to the industry as it was creating job opportunities to the citizens. He further noted that it was because of proper resource mobilization that has led to the growth of cottage industries and other financial institutions in the same country.

The study findings indicate that the number of contract beneficiaries has been improving. The number of completed social protection projects has been improving as the years progressed due to improvement in factors affecting implementation. The findings concur with Kakwezi (2012) that resources mobilization in public procurement has significant implications for service delivery through a significant reduction of time of projects completed. The analysis above shows that managerial skills have the strongest positive (Pearson correlation coefficient=0.713; P value 0.000) implementation of social projects, In addition, resources mobilization had positively correlated to the implementation of social projects.

Table 1 Correlation Coefficients

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Implementation of social protection project	Managerial skills	Resource Mobilization
Implementation of social protection project	24	0.2	1		
Managerial skills	3.57	0.138	0.713	1	
Resource Mobilization	3.87	0.228	0.632	0.394	1

*Correlation is significant at 0.02 level (1-tailed)

Multiple Regression Model Analysis

Adjusted R squared is coefficient of determination which tells us variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variables. From the findings in table 4.6, the value of adjusted R squared was 0.648, an indication that there was a variation of 64.8 percent on the implementation of social projects due to changes in managerial skills, Resources mobilization, Stakeholders Involvement, and Contract closure. The R Square, in this case, is 0.660 which clearly suggest that managerial skills, Resources mobilization shares a variation of 66% of implementation of social protection projects in Kamukunji county. Since the tabulated F (critical) (4,107) at $\alpha= 0.05$ was 2.45 which is less than F computed (11.7046) hence there is a significant effect of the independent variables, and thus the overall model is significant. As such, the model is fit significant at 5% confidence level

Managerial skills were found to have a significant positive effect on Implementation of Social protection projects ($X_{1=}$ 0.297, $P=0.000<0.05$) Shows that one unit change in Managerial skills results in 0.297-unit increase in Implementation of Social protection projects other factors held constant.

Resources Mobilization was found to have a significant positive effect on Implementation of Social protection projects ($X_{1=}$ 0.295, $P=0.000<0.05$) shows that one unit change in resources mobilization results in 0.295-unit increase in Implementation of Social protection projects other factors held constant.

Table 2 Multiple Regression Model Analysis

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Unstandardized coefficients		
	B	Std Error	Beta	T	Sig.
Constant	0.159	0.046		3.456	0.001
Managerial skills	0.297	0.04	0.463	7.425	0.00
Resource Mobilization	0.288	0.05	0.381	5.76	0.00
R	.813a				
R square	0.66				
F	11.7046				
Sig.	.013b				

a. Dependent variable: Implementation of social protection projects

Conclusions

The following indicates the conclusion of each individual objectives as per the findings.

From the findings, it's clear that managerial skills influence the implementation of social protection projects, more specifically on technical ability, interpersonal proficiency, and conceptual expertise. Technical skills influence the implementation of social protection projects, communication skills effective in implementing social protection on the beneficiaries and Interpersonal skills influence the scope of implementing projects.

Resources mobilization influences the implementation of social protection projects with more emphasis on human capability, finance availability and technological know-how. It's clear from the findings that proper Resources Mobilization has a positive influence on the implementation of social protection projects. Finance adequacy influences the implementation of social protection projects, technological infrastructure influences the implementation of social protection and human capital influences the implementation of social protection projects.

Recommendations

The study recommends that the technical capabilities of the managers and supervisors of the projects should be assessed clearly to be ascertained whether they are in a position to deliver good results. Interpersonal proficiency among the manager is very vital in driving the success of the projects. Concisely, the study recommends that commercial expertise is paramount when dealing with the projects, as such the managers should undergo adequate training for them to run the projects effectively.

The study recommends that mobilization policy should be developed to mobilize funds from other development partners of the projects. There should be health collaboration with other agencies in co funding of the social projects. The study also recommends that there must be technical know-how and infrastructure for successful implementation of the social projects.

Further research should include sustainability mechanisms, exit, and graduation. There are inadequate structures to ensure that those who no longer qualify for support are removed from the projects. Secondly research on the same factors on other counties to ascertain the factors influencing social protection projects. Additionally, these factors should be compared in different other counties. Most of the social protection funds come from development partners. This has resulted in inadequate mechanisms for financing social protection projects. In conclusion, the findings showed that 66% of the supply chain performance is explained by the four variables and the remaining 34% is accounted by the standard error.

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